

Feeding effects of rice leaffolder on flag leaf gas exchange of rice plants at flowering

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The rice leaffolder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) folds leaves and scrapes off the green tissues. LF infestations are apparent after flowering. The folding of leaves and tissue removal result in a loss of effective leaf area for photosynthesis. The relationship between infested leaf area and photosynthetic activity is not yet fully understood (de Jong 1992, Yamamoto et al 1997). Leaf gas exchange of infested flag leaves was measured to quantify this relationship, which is important for simulating changes in assimilate production and yield.

The study was conducted from 30 Aug to 16 Sep 1995 on an experimental field subjected to standard cropping management at the Kyushu National Agricultural Experiment Station, Kumamoto, Japan (32°51' N, 130°44' E). Two japonica cultivars (Hinohikari and Reiho) and one indica cultivar (IR24) were used in this study. Net photosynthesis and stomatal conductance were measured after flowering by using a LI-COR 6200 portable photosynthesis system with a 0.25-L chamber. Flag leaves folded by LF were unfolded and larvae were removed before measurement. A portion of the flag leaf blade that included the injured part was inserted into the chamber. Measurements were carried out under clear sky conditions (1450–1950 $\mu\text{mol PAR m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The leaf blades were measured and cut, and then the leaf area was measured by gas exchange with a LI-COR 3100 leaf area meter. Infested leaf area was traced with black ink onto a transparency film and measured with a leaf area meter. The photosynthetic rate of healthy flag leaves in the same plant with infested leaves was measured as the control.

No differences were observed in the reduction pattern of net photosynthesis and stomatal conductance among culti-

vars. There was a negative linear relationship between net photosynthesis and leaf area infested by LF (Fig. 1). The regression coefficients were significantly lower than 0 ($P < 0.0001$). A 10% loss in leaf area resulted in a 14–19% reduction in net photosynthesis. These values suggested that the effect of LF injury caused by the reduction in photosynthetic rate was larger than the effect of LF injury caused by reduction in leaf area.

The greater effect of LF injury on net photosynthesis was probably caused by a combination of factors such as an increase in dark respiration, a reduction in stomatal aperture, and a reduction in photosynthetic activity in the mesophyll tissue. There was a negative linear relationship between stomatal conductance and leaf area infested by LF (Fig. 2). The reduction

rate in stomatal conductance, however, was nearly the same as the reduction rate in leaf area consumed by LF. The leaf temperature of infested leaves was 0.6–1.0 °C higher than that of the control. The linear relationship between leaf area infested by LF and an increase in leaf temperature ($r^2 = 0.22$ to 0.36, $P < 0.01$) suggest an increase in dark respiration.

On an infested leaf, LF feeding reduces the leaf area and photosynthetic activity of undamaged tissues. LF feeding effects on leaf photosynthesis at flowering have not yet been introduced in simulation models to evaluate LF infestation (Benigno et al 1988, de Jong and Daamen 1992, Graf et al 1992). The effects of leaf removal by LF on total canopy photosynthesis and total assimilate production should be investigated.

Fig. 1. Relationship between percentage of leaf area infested by leaffolder larvae and net photosynthesis of flag leaf.

Fig. 2. Relationship between percentage of leaf area infested by leaffolder larvae and stomatal conductance of flag leaf.

References

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Effects of *Heterodera sacchari* population density on establishment and development of upland rice cv. IDSA6 under field and pot conditions

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In West Africa, the cyst nematode *Heterodera sacchari* is known to cause stunting and chlorosis of upland rice. Studies have also demonstrated its high pathogenicity on susceptible cultivars (Babatola 1983, Coyne and Plowright 1998).

We studied the effect of the nematode on rice (cv. IDSA6) development in a naturally infested field site at the West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA), Côte d'Ivoire, and in 100-mL pots in the greenhouse.

In the field, rice was sown at 5 seeds hill⁻¹, spaced 25 cm apart, on 60 m² of sandy soil (10% clay, 27% silt, and 63% sand) in June 1997. The area had been sown to rice cv. IDSA6 the previous year and was known to be infested with *H. sacchari*. Because of the heterogeneity of nematode occurrence, a range of infection densities over the area was expected. Other nematodes

present were *Pratylenchus zaeae*, *Meloidogyne incognita*, *Helicotylenchus dihystera*, and *Mesocriconema tesorum*. Cyst-infested soil from rice cultures was also incorporated evenly into the soil surface. Fertilizer was applied at 60 kg NPK ha⁻¹ (10:18:18) at sowing and 40 kg urea ha⁻¹ at 56 d after sowing (DAS). The experiment was maintained weed-free. At 90 DAS, 189 single hills were randomly selected and height and tiller number were recorded. Root and leaf fresh weights were measured and nematode population densities were determined from 5 g of root tissue + 100 mL of soil.

In a pot experiment replicated 10 times, seeds were sown singly into 100 mL of steam-sterilized sandy soil. Freshly hatched *H. sacchari* juveniles were inoculated in a water suspension at nine densities (see table) at sowing. Plant height was

recorded at 7 and 14 DAS and fresh root and leaf weight at 40 DAS.

In the field, *H. sacchari* reduced the growth of IDSA6. There was a negative correlation between leaf weight and *H. sacchari* juvenile population density at 90 DAS (see figure) ($r = 0.4$; $P < 0.001$). Negative correlations were also observed with root weight ($r = 0.27$; $P < 0.05$) and tiller number ($r = -0.23$; $P < 0.05$). There was no relationship between nematode population density and plant height.

In pots, very low inoculation densities appeared to have an initial stimulatory effect on plant development, but densities of 8 juveniles mL⁻¹ of soil at sowing suppressed the development of emerging seedlings. Hatching *H. sacchari* juveniles, however, emerge from their protective cysts over an extended period (Ibrahim et al 1993). Seeds germinating in the pres-